

**THE IMPORTANCE OF USING WORD GAME METHODOLOGY IN
TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN HIGHER EDUCATION
INSTITUTIONS**

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Abstract. In this article, the possibilities of using word games methodology in the process of foreign language teaching in higher education institutions are discussed, and the main attention is focused on lexical symbols in the methodology. Also, the conditions that allow effective use of the word game methodology in foreign language textbooks are justified.

Basic words and phrases: teaching a foreign language, word game methodology, dictionaries, higher education, communication, pedagogical technologies, linguistic tools, lexicon, grammar, phonetics, spelling, creative approach.

Learning a foreign language for students studying in higher education institutions opens up a number of opportunities for them in the future. In particular, graduates will be able to solve problems such as being able to communicate orally and in writing in a foreign language, enter into inter-national and interpersonal communication, move between countries without a translator, and work with documents. From this point of view, the issue discussed in this article remains relevant.

In addition, many methods are described in various textbooks, scientific works and dissertations on this topic, including: B. V. Belyayev, I. L. Bim, L. Bloomfield, E. S. Kuznetsova, E. I. Passov, I. V. Rakhmanov, E. M. Ryt, CH.

Friz, L. V. Shcherba, A. N. Shchukin and others, but their precise classification on the formation of competences has not been created.

From this point of view, the purpose of the article is to apply the word game methodology, which is often used in high school programs in the process of teaching a foreign language, to the educational processes of undergraduate education in higher education. .

To achieve the set goal, the following tasks are required:

- study and analyze the methods used in teaching foreign languages;
- use of “word game” methodologies in teaching foreign languages to students
- development of methods aimed at increasing the level of knowledge of students by using “word game” methodologies in teaching foreign languages;

Consequently, during undergraduate education, students should acquire certain knowledge (for example, knowledge of linguistic tools) and skills (use of oral communication formulas, formation of their own point of view, etc.), and should be able to communicate with international oral communication through language tools in certain situations.

Solving this complex, “global” problem requires the use of teaching methods and interactive methods with the help of rational and effective pedagogic technologies that occur throughout the entire period of foreign language teaching in higher education institutions. From this point of view, the wide use of information and communication technologies, the organization of lessons based on interactive teaching methods and a differentiated approach should be a common practice for pedagogues. At the same time, the "main element" is the foreign language teaching skills, methods and tools of the teacher who works directly with students in the classroom.

Students' knowledge of language tools, skills and their use in communication depends on how effectively the teacher delivers this material to

the requirements and reinforces it, as well as its practical application. This depends on the following methods:

Figure 1. Methods of motivating the teacher to the lesson

In modern science, word games are considered as a methodology that can be effectively used in teaching a foreign language to both children and adults. Classification of word games that can contribute to the development of certain language skills. M. F. Stronin explains as follows [1].

Figure 2. Classification of puns proposed by M. F. Stronin

The first four can be classified as so-called languages, their purpose is to develop relevant skills. Creative word games are complex in nature and involve creative application of acquired knowledge and skills in practical situations. There are other classifications of puns. For example, A. V. Konyshева divides games into linguistic and speech (communicative) games according to their purpose. E. V. Dushina talks about linguistic games and divides them into communicative and non-communicative ones depending on the competencies being formed [2]. Obviously, all given classifications are different, but they have something in common.

Figure 3. Application of word games methodology

The methodology of puns discussed in the article is explained by the word, its spelling, meaning, compatibility with other words.

stronger acquisition of familiar lexical units

get acquainted with new lexical units and expand vocabulary

Figure 4. The methodology of word games gives students the following opportunities

Word games methodology includes:

1. Anagrams
2. Crosswords
3. Search for words among chaos letters (ordsearch)
4. “The Executioner”
5. “Balda” (a word game in which you have to form words using letters added in a certain way to a square playing field).
6. “Words” (making shorter words from one long word).
7. “Opening” (composing a word from an existing set of letters).
8. Wordchain (building a list of words by replacing one letter in each subsequent word, possibly based on definitions).
9. Constructor (building words from morphemes given on separate cards).
10. “One letter - many words” (students name the words they know, starting with a certain letter of the alphabet).
11. “The last letter” (the name of the word that begins with the last letter of the previous one).
12. “Missing letters” (guessing the word with only vowels/consonants)
13. Hot Chair (guessing by definition, synonyms, antonyms, etc.) and others.

Word games, some involve working in groups, team competition (for

example, Hot Chair, Constructor, etc.), some involve working in pairs; Games such as “Hangman”, “Anagrams”, “Wordchain” are suitable for frontal play, presenting the material on the board.

The results of the survey among first-year students of Russian higher education institutions showed that the majority of students said that they like to play such a word game; While 100% of students solved crosswords with anagrams while learning English, very few students used the “Wordchain” method. In general, students found the use of word games in English classes to be “a fun, effective way to better remember the material”.

Of course, the training of the methodology of oral word play in English language classes in higher education institutions should have a positive end in itself, although in some cases it is a “rest” after hard work. can also serve. Because a positive result makes any person happy. When organizing word game methodology in foreign language classes in higher education institutions, the teacher should take into account the general methodological principles, as well as the principles of pedagogy in teaching adults. can be used.

-adults should know why they are studying this or that material. Therefore, the teacher should be ready to explain how the game helps students to learn a foreign language;

-adults see learning as problem solving, they also learn from their own experience “by doing”, and using word games can provide more opportunities for this than simple exercises in a textbook;

- the game should be carefully thought out, have clear rules and simple conditions, should be controlled by the teacher;

- the game should take place in a friendly environment, giving the student the opportunity to express himself and develop himself;

- the game should include an element of competition that can activate the mental activity of students and encourage their active participation.

Different word game methods can be used at different stages of organizing a foreign language lesson. For example, at the initial (warm-up) stage, the teacher's task is to activate students' existing knowledge and experience on a certain topic, to increase their “mood” for the mazuga, to teach students “missing letters”, “unscramble”, word games like “constructor” can start lesson processes by using methods. In this case, many of the words will be familiar to the students or likely identified based on the topic. For example, within the discussion of the general topic “Adventure holidays” in the method of the “lost letters” word game, the word “adventure” is written on the board p. can be expressed in the form of “r.u.a.t”.

Games such as “Wordsearch”, crosswords, “Unscramble” are often used to practice vocabulary on a certain topic. Such a task is widely used in school and foreign textbooks/workbooks, but textbooks for higher education institutions, especially professionals, often do not offer such an exercise-game to students. As a creative activity, the teaching technique is very effective if students create their own "letter jumble" / crossword puzzle and offer it to work in small groups in the class.

The Hot Chair method allows students to use the techniques students have learned over and over again in the lexical items/phrases texts and exercises to complete the work on the topic. The essence of the word-thinking methodology is as follows: the representative of the team must guess the word written on the board, which may be suggested by the teacher or another team, based on the suggestions and explanations of his team. In this, the student sits with his back to the board and does not see the word, only the teacher or a representative from another team explains the meaning of the word. And the student, by expressing his opinion, shows that student creativity tries to explain and convey the knowledge obtained from other subjects in a foreign language.

By encouraging students to express their thoughts in a foreign language,

they engage in communication, practice the skills of constructing sentences, and practice certain speech formulas. At the same stage, students usually think actively, offer options, do not want to end up losing in a word game.

"WordChain" method can be used for training with elementary students because it often contains short, simple words of 3-4 letters. However, if modified word definitions are used, the task becomes more difficult for students. Some games focus on spelling and can be used to introduce new words.

Based on the issues discussed in the article, we can conclude the following.

Each teacher presents material to students based on his own developed and proven methodology. At the same time, there are some methods and tools, the use of which has been proven in many experiments to qualitatively increase the level of knowledge of students. One of these methods is the methodology of word games, which encourages students to think broadly, acquire a wealth of vocabulary, and increase knowledge and experience.

In applying the word game methodology, the teacher should not “take on the burden” of the whole activity - but transfer part of the work to the students, for example, transfer the lexical units of the word game methodology within the topic, so they feel responsible for the correct solution of the material, exercises in the word game methodology. and in this case, the use of word-thinking methodology in foreign language lessons actually becomes an effective pedagogic technique.

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